

Impact of Structured Physical Activity in Type 2 Diabetes: A Prospective Randomised Control StudyDipankar Prakas Bhaumik¹, Mukut Roy², Kaushik Tripura³, Sulata Das⁴¹Associate Professor, Department of Medicine, Tripura Medical College and Dr. BRAM Teaching Hospital. Agartala, Tripura²Consultant Endocrinologist & In charge Endocrinology division, Ex - Professor, Department of Medicine, Tripura Medical College and Dr. BRAM Teaching Hospital. Agartala, Tripura³Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Tripura Medical College and Dr. BRAM Teaching Hospital. Agartala, Tripura⁴Medical Officer, Tripura Health Service, GB hospital, Agartala, Tripura

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Abstract:

Introduction: Physical activity provides multiple benefits to the patients with diabetes mellitus (DM) as it can increase cellular insulin sensitivity by reducing inflammation and obesity. Moderate habitual physical activity has positive impact on health in diabetes mellitus, pre-diabetes and people with increased insulin resistance¹. Different studies has shown that structured physical exercise can reduce glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) to the extent of 0.6%. Non-structured physical activities like strolling, gardening, household tasks are also beneficial. Tripura is having high prevalence of diabetes (9.4%) and pre-diabetes(14.7 %). So this study is highly relevant in the context of the region.

Materials and Methods: The study was started with scientific and ethical approval on 1st April 2017 as a project work for the Distance Fellowship in Diabetes Management (DFID) from the Endocrinology Department, Christian Medical College, Vellore). The study had been continued till 31st March 2024 at two different clinics of the authors. 920 patients considering inclusion (age group of 18 years to 64 years) and exclusion criteria (comorbidities contraindicated for exercise, physical condition causing limitation, acute and poor general condition and not willing to participate) were included in the study with primary objective to estimate the impact of structured physical exercise on glycaemic status and secondary objective to estimate the impact on weight, body mass index (BMI) and lipid profile. Subjects were enrolled after obtaining informed written consent. After ensuring benefits of Medical Nutrition Therapy (MNT), patients were randomised by simple lottery to intervention (Gr A) and non-intervention (GrB) groups. Intervention group received detail counselling on structured exercise. All the subjects were followed for 3 months. A total of 870 patients completed the study.

Results: There was greater weight and BMI reduction in intervention group with statistically significant difference. HbA1c, Fasting and Post prandial blood sugar reduction was also better in exercise arm in the study though change of these parameters in both the groups were significant. In addition, there was improvement in lipid parameters.

Conclusion: This study demonstrates significant improvement of anthropometric and metabolic parameters in the intervention group which imply additional benefit of physical exercise in addition to benefits of MNT. All these benefits were independent of effect of metformin.

Keywords: Structured Physical Activity, Type 2 Diabetes, Medical Nutrition Therapy, Metformin.

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Introduction

Physical activity provides multiple benefits to the patients with diabetes mellitus (DM) as it can increase cellular insulin sensitivity by reducing inflammation and obesity. Moderate habitual physical activity has positive impact on health in type 2 diabetes mellitus(T2DM), pre-diabetes and people with increased insulin resistance[1]. One of the three cornerstones of diabetes management is exercise beside dietary modification and

medication[2,3]. Physical exercise for 8 weeks can reduce glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) by 0.66% among T2DM patients even without significant change in Body Mass index (BMI)[4]. In a meta-analysis of 14 studies, HbA1c reduction in T2DM was 0.6% greater in exercise group as compared with controls (p < 0.05)[5]. In addition to structured exercise, other physical activities like strolling, gardening, and household tasks are also

beneficial for glycaemic control. Therefore, patients should be encouraged for regular such activities[6]. In a recent study of 300 subjects, HbA1c change in structured exercise training group found to be 0.69% (95% CI, 0.62-0.75%; $P \geq 0.02$) in comparison to 0.24% (95% CI, 0.19 - 0.31%; $P \geq 0.09$) in unstructured activity group[7]. The majority of studies which supplement weight reduction and exercise programs with appropriate drug therapy have been done on western population. Tripura is having high prevalence of diabetes (9.4%) and higher prevalence of pre-diabetics (14.7 %) in India[8]. There is an absolute paucity of studies conducted in India or conducted on Indian population; hence the proposed study carries significance and relevance. So the study is highly relevant in the context of the region, more so because, physical activity is cost effective means of diabetes management.

Materials and Methods

The study was started on 1st April 2017 as a project work for DFID, with the guidance of Department of Endocrinology, Christian Medical College (CMC), Vellore. Scientific and ethical approval was obtained from institutional committee of CMC, Vellore. The study had been continued till 31st March 2024, it was conducted at two different private clinics of the authors at Agartala, Tripura, India. All the patients attending clinics, fulfilling inclusion criteria were included in the study with primary objective to estimate the impact of structured physical exercise on glycaemic status and secondary objective to estimate the impact on weight, BMI and lipid profile. All the subjects were followed for 3 months.

Inclusion Criteria: Adult Type 2 diabetes Mellitus patients of the age group of 18 years to 64 years.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Co-morbidities contraindicated for exercise e.g. Congestive Cardiac Failure (CCF), Peripheral Vascular Disease (PVD).
2. Physical condition causing limitation e.g. amputation, deformity etc.
3. Acute and Poor general condition.
4. Not willing to participate.

Subjects were enrolled after obtaining informed written consent. Fasting and Post prandial plasma sugar (FBS, PPBS), glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) and relevant investigations were done at induction and medications were adjusted. Routine evaluation for cardio-vascular diseases (CVD) with electrocardiography(ECG) and six-minute walk test and Peripheral Vascular Disease (PVD) was done though pre-exercise medical clearance is not necessary for asymptomatic individuals receiving diabetes care consistent with guidelines⁹.

Counselling on medical nutrition therapy (MNT) was given to all enrolled subjects. Adherence was reviewed every two weeks until satisfactory level was achieved. 4 weeks elapse time allowed thereafter to attain benefit of MNT before structured physical exercise was introduced. Before randomization, body weight, BMI, FBS and PPBS, HbA1c, lipid profile was measured. Then participants were randomized in to two groups by lottery. Group A (intervention group) subjects were given counselling and training for physical exercise in presence of family members. Exercise schedule was covering warm up for 5 to 10 min, aerobics e.g. walking, swimming, cycling, jogging, etc for 30 to 40 minute for 5 days / week, at least for 3 days / week exercise, with no gap of more than 2 days and covering minimum of 150 min in week⁹ followed by cooling down for 5 to 10 minute, strength building exercise for 10minute for 3 days / week, and stretching/flexibility increasing exercises for 10 minute for 3 days / week. All patients opted for walking though other options were given. Protective measures and symptoms of hypoglycemia were explained to each individual². It was emphasized to achieve target heart rate, with intensification of exercise, if required. Group B (non-intervention group) subjects were advised to continue with dietary modification advised earlier. Review visit in every 2 weeks for next three month was advised to subjects of both the group, maximum patients failed to come, so we accepted 3 follow up monthly visit including a visit at the completion of 3 month as valid subject. In each follow up visit or call, enforcement of counselling was done to improve adherence. Weight, FBS and PPBS were measured during every visit. HbA1c was repeated after 3 months from randomization. In this study, taking predicted HbA1c difference 0.65% (SD of effect of 1.2 HbA1c units, $\alpha = 0.05$, $1 - \beta = 0.85$, expected drop-out 15%) power and sample size calculation yielded at least of 61 participants. Statistical analysis was done using SPSS, Version 22 software. Levene's test was done to test the equality of variance. Paired t test, Welch's t test, Wilcoxon rank test, Mann – whitney test were used as required. Two-sided probability values ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results and Observations

A total 1089 enrolled diabetics were explained about the study and 1028 (94.39%) patients gave consent of participation. 108 patients were excluded due to co-morbid medical conditions and possible unavailability in follow-up. 920 patients were included in the study and divided equally to group A (intervention group) and Group B (non-intervention group) by simple lottery.

Chart 1:

Drop out from the intervention group was 31 (6.74%) (3 patients changed location, 9 lost contact, 2 patients opted to withdraw, 1 couple met RTA, 3 had sepsis, 2 had myocardial infarction, 1 had cerebral infarction. 2 had psychological issues). Drop out in non-intervention group was 19 (4.13%)(7 lost in follow up, 3 UTI sepsis, 3 myocardial infarction, 2 cerebral infarction, 2 CAP and 2 patients expired). A distribution considered

to be normal if skewness falls between -1 and 1 and values of kurtosis fall between - 2 and + 2. Levene’s test was done to test the equality of variance. Fasting sugar was higher in intervention group. Mean weight, BMI, Post Prandial Sugar and HbA1c was higher in non-intervention group. Other parameters were grossly matching in both the group.

Table 1: Base line variables

Variable	Intervention Group (n-429)	Non – Intervention (n-441)
Age (year)	53.1 ± 13.1*	53.2 ± 8.94*
Male (Total 434, 49.88%)	205 (47.8%)	229 (51.9%)
Female (Total 436, 50.11%)	224 (52.2%)	212 (48.1%)
Lifestyle	Sedentary	192 (44.8%)
	Moderate	155 (36.1%)
	Strenuous	82 (19.1%)
DM duration (Year)	5 (2 – 8)**	6 (4 – 9)**
Height (meter)	1.57 ± 0.087*	1.59 ± 0.091*
Weight (Pre) (Kg)	63.5 ± 12.1*	66.3 ± 10.4*
BMI (kg/1.72m ²)	25.9 ± 4.52*	26.4 (±3.75)*
Fasting sugar (mg/dL)	152 ± 36.8*	144 (126 – 173)**
PP sugar (mg/dL)	226 ± 74.8*	299 ± 70.2*
HbA1C (%)	7.10 (6.80 – 7.80)**	7.20 (6.80 – 8.10)**
Cholesterol ((mg/dL))	172 (150 – 206)**	171 (150 – 205)**
Triglyceride ((mg/dL))	170 (130 – 280)**	181 (124 – 247)**
HDL((mg/dL))	42 (34.6 – 47)**	42 (38 – 46.2)**
LDL((mg/dL))	116 ± 44.1*	103 (83 – 125)**
VLDL((mg/dL))	32 (25 – 52)**	32 (23 – 44)**
Mean ± SD*, Median (IQR)**		

Table 2: Distribution of patients taking metformin

		Intervention Group		Non Intervention Group		Total
Male	With Metformin	128	205	177	229	434
	Without Metformin	77		52		
Female	With Metformin	125	224	173	212	436
	Without Metformin	99		39		
Total		429 (Metformin 253)		441 (Metformin 350)		870

In the intervention group 253 (58.97%), in non-intervention group 350 (79.37%), altogether 603 (69.3%) patients were on metformin separately or in combination as part of diabetes medication.

Table 3: Change of parameters at study completion

Variable	Intervention group		Mean difference (95% CI)	P value	Non-Intervention group		Mean difference (95% CI)	p value
	Pre intervention	Post intervention			Pre intervention	Post intervention		
Weight	63.5 ± 12.1	61.5 ± 10.6	2.03 (1.81 – 2.24)	0.001 *	66.3 ±10.42	65.5 ± 9.89	0.820 (0.714 – 0.927)	0.001 *
BMI	25.9 ± 4.52	25.1 ± 4.07	0.795 (0.708 – 0.882)	0.001*	26.4 (3.75)	26.1 (3.56)	0.320 (0.276 – 0.364)	0.001 *
FPS	152 ± 36.8	120 ± 18.0	32.2 (29.6 – 34.7)	0.001 *	144 (126 – 173)	126 (110 – 146)	-	0.001 **
PPS	212 (168 - 268)	168 (144 - 188)	-	0.001 **	218 (176 – 285)	186 (158 – 212)	-	0.001 **
HbA1C	7.10 (6.80 – 7.80)	6.60 (6.30 – 6.80)	-	0.001* *	7.20 (6.80 – 8.10)	6.90 (6.50 – 7.50)	-	0.001 **
Cholesterol	172 (150 – 206)	120 (102 – 132)	-	0.001 **	171 (150 – 205)	123 (112 – 143)	-	0.001 **
Triglyceride	170 (130 – 280)	134 (120 – 158)	-	0.001 **	181 (124 – 246)	148 (121 – 184)	-	0.001 **
HDL	42 (34 – 47)	49 (44 – 56)	-	0.001 **	42 (38 – 46.2)	48 (43 – 52)	-	0.001 **
LDL	104 (104 – 139)	88 (74 – 112)	-	0.001 **	103 (83 – 125)	96 (78 – 112)	-	0.001 **
VLDL	32 (25 – 52)	27 (24 – 31)	-	0.001 **	32 (23 – 44.8)	29 (24 – 37)	-	0.001 **

FBS- Fasting Plasma Sugar, PPS – Post Prandial Plasma Sugar, HbA1c – Glycated haemoglobin, BMI – Body Mass Index,
 Mean ± SD, Median (IQR), Paired t test (*), Wilcoxon rank test (**), p value <0.05 taken as a significance

Figure 1: Comparison of changes in intervention and non-intervention group

(Welch's t test (*), Mann – Whitney test (**), p value <0.05 taken as a significance)

Weight change (2.03 ± 2.30 Kg Vs 0.820 ± 1.14 , p 0.001*) and BMI change (0.794 ± 0.919 Vs 0.320 ± 0.465 , p) in both the arm of study was significant though it was much greater in intervention group. Observation was similar in respect of fasting blood sugar (26 (10 - 52) mg /dL Vs 16(8-24) mg /dL), post prandial blood sugar (36(10 - 78) mg /dL Vs 30 (14 - 46) mg /dL) and glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) {0.5% (from 7.1% to 6.6%) Vs 0.3%

(from 7.2% to 6.9%)} as changes were statistically significant and the differences between two group was too significant.

Changes of all the parameters of lipid profile were significant in both intervention group and non-intervention group of study population. 69.3% of the study population was taking metformin, which is known agent to lower blood sugar, HbA1c and improve BMI. To see influence of metformin, findings were further analysed in relation to metformin intake.

Table 4 A: Comparison of intervention subgroup on metformin and without metformin

Variables	Intervention group with Metformin	Intervention group without Metformin	Mean difference (95% CI)	p - value
Weight reduction (kg)	2.10 ± 2.46	1.92 ± 2.05	0.178 (- 0.252 – 0.608)	0.416 *
BMI reduction	0.815 ± 0.981	0.763 ± 0.823	0.0519 (-0.120 – 0.224)	0.553*
FPS reduction (mg/dL)	33.4 ± 27	30.4 ± 27.5	2.96 (-2.30 – 8.23)	0.269 *
PPS reduction (mg/dL)	36 (14 - 84)	34 (10 - 78)	-	0.216 **
HbA1C (%) reduction	0.500 (0.300 – 0.800)	0.520 (0.300 – 0.900)	-	0.971**

FPS – Fasting Plasma Sugar, PPS – Postprandial Plasma Sugar, Mean \pm SD, Median (IQR), Welch's t test(*), Mann – whitney test(**), p value <0.05 taken as a significance

Weight, BMI, FBS, PPBS, HbA1c reduction in metformin subgroup is better than sub group not on metformin with in intervention group, though differences were not statistically significant.

Table 4B: Comparison of subgroup of patients with metformin in intervention group and non-intervention group

Variables	Intervention group with Metformin	Non-Intervention group with Metformin	Mean difference (95% CI)	p value
Weight reduction (kg)	2.10 ± 2.46	0.950 ± 1.16	1.15 (0.821 – 1.48)	0.001*
BMI reduction	0.815 ± 0.981	0.372 ± 0.475	0.443 (0.312 – 0.574)	0.001*
FPS reduction (mg/dL)	28 (12 - 46)	16(8 - 24)	-	0.001**
PPS reduction (mg/dL)	36(14 - 84)	30(14 - 45)	-	0.001**
HbA1C (%) reduction	0.500 (0.300 – 0.800)	0.300 (0.200 – 0.580)	-	0.001**

FPS – Fasting Plasma Sugar, PPS – Postprandial Plasma Sugar, Mean \pm SD, Median (IQR), Welch's t test(*), Mann – whitney test(**), p value <0.05 taken as a significance

Weight, BMI, FBS, PPBS, HbA1c reduction in metformin subgroup of intervention group was better than metformin subgroup of non-intervention group (p= 0.001).

Table 4 C: Comparison of subgroup patients without metformin in intervention group and non-intervention group

Variables	Intervention group without Metformin	Non-Intervention group without Metformin	Mean difference (95% CI)	p value
Weight reduction (kg)	1.92 ± 2.05	0.321 ± 0.866	1.60 (1.25 – 1.95)	0.001*
BMI reduction	$0.730(0.00 – 1.40)$	$0.0800(0.080 – 0.350)$	-	0.001**
FPS reduction (mg/dL)	20 (7 - 53)	16(7.50 - 26)	-	0.050**
PPS reduction (mg/dL)	34(10 - 78)	33(19 - 52)	-	0.661**
HbA1C (%) reduction	0.520(0.300– 0.900)	0.400(0.300 – 0.600)	-	0.001**

FPS – Fasting Plasma Sugar, PPS – Postprandial Plasma Sugar, Mean \pm SD, Median (IQR), Welch's t test(*), Mann – Whitney test(**), p value <0.05 taken as a significance

Comparison reveals that weight, BMI, HbA1c reduction in non-metformin sub-group of intervention group was significantly better whereas differences of FBS and PPS reduction was not statistically significant.

Discussion

In current study weight reduction was 2.05kg and 0.82 kg in intervention group and non-intervention group respectively with a significant difference where as Sanghani N B et al observed change of -3.7 kg (p - 0.21) in the structured exercise training group, though the change was not statistically significant⁷. In another small study, keeping calorie deficit constant during 6-month trial, 10% weight loss was achieved in both exercise group and non-exercise group without a statistically significant difference between groups. However, the exercise group had the added benefit of improved aerobic fitness[10]. Ross et al. demonstrated 7.5 kg decrease in body weight over 3 months in the exercise-only group that was comparable to that of the calorie-restricted group[11]. All these findings indicate exercise can reduce weight better along with calorie restricted diet, in accordance with our study. One study has found, physical exercise alone is not better than diet but combination is better than both exercise and diet[12]. We ensured medical nutrition therapy in all subjects before starting of the study. 69.3% of study population was taking metformin. That explains significant weight loss in the control group; physical exercise had additional impact on weight reduction in intervention group. Physical activity of all types, including aerobic, resistance, flexibility exercises and reduced sedentary time clearly results in multiple health benefits and encouraging individuals to exercise for longer periods of time each day may help to enhance weight loss[13]. The scientific evidence presented in the Physical Activity Guidelines Committee Report in the United States confirms that physical activity alone typically results in weight change of <3% of initial weight (0.5 kg to 3.0kg), this is again similar with the report of 2.4 kg reduction by National Heart Lung and Blood Institutes Expert Panel[14].

In the present study, BMI reduction was 0.794 ± 0.919 (p - 0.001) in intervention group, and 0.320 ± 0.465 (0.001) in non-intervention group with a significant difference of mean {0.474(0.377-0.571)} between the groups (p - 0.001). In one Indian study, BMI reduced from 30.03 ± 4.12 kg/m² to 29.37 ± 3.13 kg/m² with structured physical activity but in control group it increased from 29.84 ± 3.03 kg/m² to 30.12 ± 2.26 Kg/m² with no significant post-intervention differences[7]. Evidence from the Canadian NPHS panel states that by adopting leisure time low grade activity, reduces BMI by about 0.11–0.14 points in males

and 0.20 points in females relative to physically inactive counterparts whereas adopting lifting of loads in working environment can reduce BMI by 0.2–0.3 points in males and 0.3–0.4 points in females in comparison to sedentary counterparts¹⁵. In another study, exercise group enjoyed BMI reduction of -2.7kg/m² after 24 months but physical exercise with metformin group observed reduction of -1.4kg/m². Both the changes were significant[16]. In another study, aerobic exercise reduced BMI from 27.2 ± 2.2 to 26.8 ± 2.3 by 6 weeks but was not sustainable[17]. Present study findings were similar with other studies, indicating regular physical exercise in combination with dietary measure can attain better result.

Median of fasting blood sugar reduction was more with exercise group, non-intervention arm also had significant reduction. Inter group difference was also significant (p - 0.001). Lale B et al found higher reduction of fasting sugar with aerobic exercise in comparison to vibration exercise though comparison was not significant[18]. In another study, reduction of fasting sugar was observed with walking[19].

Significant difference was observed in regards of PPBS reduction. Another study found positive effect in reducing PPBS with exercise[20]. Multiple studies concluded - high-intensity interval training and moderate-intensity continuous training causes significant reduction in “time in hyperglycemia” and improves area under the curve (AUC) significantly[19,21]. Our study also emphasizes role of exercise for better post prandial sugar control.

There was better reduction of HbA1c (0.4%) with physical exercise while comparing with metformin (p - 0.179) in one study[16]. In another study, HbA1C did not reduce significantly during 6 weeks aerobic training but did rise significantly during the detraining period[17]. Another study had shown that 6 month cycling reducing HbA1c by 1.18 % (p-0.001)[22]. One study has shown HbA1c reduction by 0.3 with walking but HbA1c reduction was significantly higher with antigravity exercise[19]. Our patients were getting benefit of MNT and intervention group got better reduction of HbA1c due to additional effect of exercise.

In a study, exercise group showed reduction of cholesterol (p - <0.001) and triglyceride (p - 0.941)[16]. In another study, significant improvements to all the body composition of lipid profile was seen[17]. After 8 weeks of aerobic exercise training, one study demonstrated improvement of lipid profile with a discernible decrease in triglyceride, total cholesterol and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol. There was an increase in high density lipoprotein cholesterol[23]. Findings of our study also correlate with these

findings. One longitudinal study with older diabetics (T2DM), with co-morbidities, in the early stage of the disease (mean HbA1c percentage < 7.5%) shown that exercise is better effective therapy to reduce sugar, HbA1c and CV risk factors than metformin[16]. The finding is similar to our findings. However, limitations of the study show that this was conducted with type 2 diabetes patients of any duration and all the patients were aware of life style management to certain extent. Study with all newly diagnosed patients probably would have given better results regarding impact of physical exercise on glycaemic status in T2 Diabetes Mellitus patients.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates significant improvement of anthropometric and metabolic parameters in the intervention group which imply added benefit of structured physical activity in addition to benefits of MNT. All these benefits were independent of effect of metformin. It also may be concluded that regular structured physical activity brings benefit to type 2 diabetes patients in respect of glycaemic, weight reduction and lipid profile. So, health care providers should encourage the patients with type 2 diabetes to incorporate structured physical activity in their life and play a proactive role.

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